

The Collatz prime conjecture: numerical results

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Let $C_3(t)$ be the Collatz function

$$C_3(t) = (3t + 1)/2 \quad \text{for } t \text{ odd}$$

Call a prime p a 'Collatz' prime if $C_3(p)$ is also prime.

Let

$$\pi(x) = \#\{\text{primes } p: 2 < p \leq x\}$$

be the prime counter starting at 3, and $\sigma(x)$ the Collatz primes counter:

$$\sigma(x) = \#\{\text{Collatz primes } p: 2 < p \leq x\}$$

In a previous article [1], the Collatz Primes Conjecture proposed that

$$\sigma(x) \rightarrow \pi(x)/\lambda \log_{10}(\pi(x)) \quad \text{for sufficiently large } x, \text{ where } \lambda = 2.$$

Numerical testing of primes incrementing up to $x = \text{ten billion}$ (455,052,511 primes) indicates that a far better estimate for λ is

$$\lambda = 1.953$$

for a long-term absolute percentage error of **0.00234**, at least in the range considered here.

The charts below contrast the long-term errors:

With $\lambda = 2$ (above) the initially erratic errors did begin to decrease eventually until $x = \text{ten million}$ (664,579 primes) to about .04%; however, this trend reversed later on, the errors actually increasing to 2.34% at $x = \text{ten billion}$. Of course, this trend in the wrong direction might itself reverse in a longer prime train.

The better estimate of $\lambda = 1.953$ tells a different story (see below):

While equally erratic initially and unpromising for a while, errors began to fall below 1% after $x =$ four hundred million (21,336,326 primes) and decreased steadily thereafter to 0.00234% at $x =$ ten billion, and likely beyond.

The availability of an increasing sample of primes for this numerical testing allowed another numerical comparison; with

$$\pi(x) = \#\{\text{primes } p: 2 \leq p \leq x\}$$

the usual primes counter, consider instead the estimates

$$\pi_{\lambda}(x) = x / (\ln(x) - \lambda)$$

Thus

$$\pi_0(x) = \text{PNT}$$

and

$$\pi_1(x) = \text{Chebyshev}$$

It turned out that the small change to $\lambda = 1.05$ improved even the Chebyshev estimate, both far superior to PNT up to $x =$ ten billion; this latter error did not fall below 4% even at that large count!

First the Chebyshev %error chart for $\lambda = 1$; see below.

The last estimated error at $x = \text{ten billion}$ was 0.22866%, respectable but appeared steady-state. By contrast, the small change to $\lambda = 1.05$ reached an error of 0.00166% at the same terminus with a further decreasing trend; see chart below.

Reference

[1] A. Cusmariu, 'The Collatz Primes Conjecture', 10.5281/zenodo.10879715, 2024